

VARIETY OF WAYANG KULIT PURWA IN MALANG: AN AUTOETNOGRAPHY STUDY

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Abstract: *This study aims to describe the diversity of wayang kulit purwa in Malang Raya. The formulation of the problem in this research is the kind of wayang kulit purwa in Malang. Along with these objectives and problems, the method used is the autoethnographic research method based on field research. This research was started in 1998. In conducting research, researchers used to interview and documentation methods. The results showed that in Malang there were several kinds of wayang kulit purwa. Researchers classified the types of wayang kulit purwa in Malang into two groups, namely: made by poor people, and products from outside the region. Wayang Kulit Purwa, made by Malang people, is divided into ndusun puppets and wayang prayung. The production of wayang from outside the region is divided into sub-style Central Java and East Java. The various wayang kulit in Malang each have various expressions and carry out a social function as a reflection of personal and community behavior. The development of wayang kulit purwa in Malang is influenced by various situations of the era and stages of the shadow puppet performance art.*

Keywords: *Variety, Wayang Kulit, Malang, Autoethnography*

INTRODUCTION

One form of culture is present in people's lives in the form of artificial objects (artifacts) or physical culture. The artwork is an important embodiment of one of the universal cultural elements. Indonesia is very rich in traditional arts and cultural heritage, including wayang kulit art

On November 7, 2003, wayang was recognized by UNESCO as the Master Piece of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity, this shows that wayang has a high ranking and is recognized at the international cultural level. Whereas at the national level, wayang is a noble legacy from the ancestors of the Indonesian people who have productivity in the hearts of the people, especially the Javanese [1].

One of the puppet genres that is widely developed in society is the Malangan shadow puppet genre. Regarding the form of the shadow puppet genre in Malang, Christianto [2] expressed his opinion about the form of wayang kulit in Malang, namely "In the Malang region there is a puppet tradition which is similar to the tradition in the

East Java, but the people of Malang and the traditional group of the people of East Java call it the "Malangan Tradition".

Wayang kulit with the Malangan style is a performance art featuring plays or stories from the Ramayana and Mahabarata epics, as well as shadow puppet performances in other regions (Central Java, Yogyakarta Special Region, and other areas). Geographically, the Malangan shadow puppet tradition is in the Greater Malang area.

The world of wayang kulit performance in the Malangan style has not attracted much interest among writers and art researchers in Indonesia because it is considered a coastal art that is considered less attractive than the art world in the Kraton (Yogyakarta and Surakarta). The performing arts of wayang kulit and shadow puppets in the Malangan style are the world of folk performing arts that do not get much interference from the interests of the palace from various social, political, cultural, and other pragmatic aspects. It grows naturally in the village of heirs and custodians of its traditions according to its dynamics and level of knowledge.

Initial observations of the world of wayang kulit styles in Malangan can be seen through the writing of Karya Soenarto Timoer (1988) which discusses East Java shadow puppet shows. Meanwhile, Umar Kayam (2001) in his book entitled *Kelir Tanpa Batas* touches on the general picture of the East Java shadow puppet art world in general. However, a slightly in-depth discussion of Wayang Malangan is only found in the research of Suyanto (2002) which at a macro level discusses the dynamic characteristics of wayang kulit in Malang as part of the East Javanese style tradition. From some of the literature above, it appears that research on the Malangan style wayang kulit has not been studied as seriously as the study of traditional Javanese shadow puppet performance.

One of the things that have not been seriously studied in the Malangan-style wayang kulit is the diversity of wayang types that exist in this sub-genre. One of the characteristics of wayang kulit is the shadow puppets used in the show. Wayang has a prominent function in wayang performances because from there the audience can be guided to be able to narratively understand what stories the dalang is telling.

Knowing this, the researcher then raised the issue to be discussed in this journal, namely.

1. How is the history of wayang kulit in Malang?
2. How is the process of making leather puppets in Malang?
3. How are the various leather puppets in Malang?
4. What is the function of the wayang kulit in Malang?
5. Who are the shadow puppet craftsmen in Malang?

In line with the above problems, this research then raises the title "Variety of Wayang Kulit in Malang: Auto-Ethical Studies" to describe Wayang Kulit in Malang City.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research was conducted using field research methods with an autoethnographic approach. According to Chang [3]. Autoethnographers have full access to our experiences and interpretations of what happened in the past. Also,

autoethnography is first hand in choosing which memories are relevant in the research conducted. One of the things that are emphasized in writing autoethnography is the collection of memory data.

Memories or memories are important in autoethnography writing. Memories are what makeup who we are today. "Recalling" or remembering an event in autoethnographic research has the same principle as what ethnographic research from other genres does [3]. Meanwhile, in the field of autoethnography, the writer has its advantages. As authors, we have full access to our experiences and interpretations of what happened in the past. Also, we are the first hand to choose which memories are relevant in our study [3].

This autoethnographic research was started in 1998 by Yudit Perdananto by visiting all puppeteers in Malang. In the following years, the second and third authors helped the data search process. To support the research process, Autoethnography can be scientifically justified. In the process of searching for data, the researcher wrote field data in the form of notes and used other data to triangulate the validity of the data (interviews, observations, library data, and artifacts).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

History of Wayang Kulit in Malang

Malang has been an open area since the Dutch colonization. At that time economic planning had begun, becoming an international route (through Surabaya) which opened access to the surrounding area. Malang was officially occupied by the Dutch colonial government since 1767 after the Dutch broke the resistance of Prince Singosari-Malayakusuma, a descendant of Suropati. The takeover of the Malayakusuma prince was included in the gebied rechtstreeksestuurd (an area directly controlled by the Dutch) and in 1771 officially became one of the districts in the Karisedenan Pasuruan region [4].

Since then the names of Malang Regent have been recorded, including Raden Tumenggung Kertanegara (....-1822), Raden Regent Panji Wilasmoro (1823-1839), Raden Tumenggung Noto Diningrat (1839-1884), Raden Tumenggung Ario Noto Diningrat (1884- 1898)), Suryo Adi Ningrat (1898-1934), and Ario Adipati SA. M (1934-1942).

In 1767 the population of Malang was estimated to be around 1000 households. The distance between Malang and Pasuruan is about 50 km which can be reached by using a cart for about two days. Meanwhile, the southern area of Malang is overgrown with shrubs and inhabited by rioters. This means that the South Malang area has not been opened, either for agricultural land or for plantations. The Lawang area (north of Malang) was opened for the first time because the land is fertile and the air is cool. This allows it to be used as a (cultural) coffee plantation. In 1800 the Malang area generally became agricultural fields and coffee plantations.

Pigeaud's report (1938) states that housing and the economy in Malang have been developing for a long time. One of the regents who leads the Malang region is Regent Ario Adipati S.A.M. which ruled between 1934-1942. This period is the reign of the Malang Regent before the independence of the Republic of Indonesia.

The oldest wayang kulit in Malang was found in 1845 AD, owned by a rich man who was a relative of the 2nd Malang Regent. In 1887 M soerang named Sastro from the Tengger area made a wayang kulit which is now kept by his son. The local community then called it Wayang ndusun.

In 1901 in the village of Babakan Karangploso, a wayang golek was found, according to the puppet owner from the Tumpang area. In the puppet era, Ki Sastro Amijaya's framed wayang was found in 1924 from Simpar Village, in 1930 belonging to Pak Wahyudi from Gandul Lawang Village, and in 1933 from Babatan Permanu Village. Wayang Ki Sastro Amijaya is a ndusun puppet, while the puppet daeri from Gandul and Babatan villages is Wayang Gresik or commonly known as Wayang Pesisiran.

At the time of Regent Ario Adipati S.A.M. in the 1930s. A man named Reni and some of his relatives, a Malang Wayang Topeng maestro created a genre innovation called "Mangkunegaran Malangan". Based on Ongkhoham's search, Reni's work belonged to a relative in Jabung.

"Reni has another younger brother, Nita, who is no less famous as a shadow puppet carver. Both Reni and Nita abandoned their sons, Reni's daughter sold the famous Reni gamelan and also the mask and shadow puppet business after their death (Reni and Nita) to relatives in Jabung [5]."

During the Reni period, VII Mangkunegara opened the widest possible access to see, observe, and research artists, researchers, and cultural observers from all regions in Java, one of which was Malang. Mangkunegara VII was the ruler of Vorstenlanden who initiated a movement that attempted to study and re-actualize Javanese culture of the past and that period, to determine the direction of cultural development in the future along with the rapid development of Western culture [6]. Mangkunegara VII then initiated the establishment of the Java Institute (Java Institute). It is an organization working to develop Javanese, Madurese, Sundanese, and Balinese language, literature, and culture. Javanese and Dutch work together in organizations. Initially, there were 50 members, half of whom were European. The patron of this institution is the Governor-General Prangwedana who was appointed as the honorary chairman and RA Dr. Hoesein Djajadiningrat's son-in-law as a daily chairman [7]. Mangkunegara VII was very interested in the world of puppetry. He was also so enthusiastic about the Panji-Raden Damarwulan story that he compiled a text describing wayang krucil [8].

In the 1950-1969 era, generations of wayang makers were born in the hamlets of Malang. The work of these craftsmen is then called wayang ndusun. Some of the puppet craftsmen that can be traced include Pak Surya and Pak Salya from Wajak Village (1950); Pak Kansen, Pak Darlin, and Pak Darso from Jabung village (1960); Pak Isno from the village of Wajak (1965); Pak Isman from the village of Jatikerto (1965); and Pak Tulin from Briyut (1965).

During the New Order era and protected by cronies of President Soeharto, the Surakarta puppet was promoted as an essential form of Javanese tradition in festivals, publications, and other public representations. Wayang became a "train-merchandise" or luxury goods [9]. In East Java in the 1980s, local puppeteers had to adopt aspects of

the Surakarta style to continue to compete [10]. The puppeteers in Central and East Java then bought the Surakarta-style leather puppets which were colorful and light, so this style of play was popularized in the 1980s by Solo-style puppeteer Ki Manteb Soedharsono, and the old puppeteer selling puppets. antique seller, although it has long been used as a seed or model for wayang making. Regional patterns in these years began to form minorities and were threatened with extinction [11].

To reduce the hegemony of the Surakarta-style wayang golek, some shadow puppet craftsmen from the Malang area have started to adapt the form of the Surakarta-style puppet show and several other Central Javanese styles to maintain its existence, besides that the need for wayang performances is also needed. there. increased rapidly so that new puppet craftsmen began to appear. Some of the puppet makers that year were: Pak Dasuki from Pohbener Wagir complained, Pak Darto from Lawang, Pak Dollah from Jeruk (Lowokwaru), Pak Jani Karanglo, Pak Bromo from Simpar, Pak Suud from Bunder Tumpang Village, Pak Wibisono from Pesanggrahan Batu, Pak Andre from Punten Batu, Pak Pinto from Ngumbal Ngantang, and Pak Raspan from Klayatan Malang City. People from the Malang area call this adaptation work Wayang Pegon. Whereas the people of Surakarta are called Wayang Prayung because the shadow puppets made by Malang people seem gray, not driven by Yogyakarta, Surakarta, or East Java styles but more like individual interpretations of how good wayang is adapted from various genres.

In the 1980s, several migrant craftsmen began to settle in Malang, such as Pak Cipto from the Blitar Surakarta style, Pak Kondo Suharto from the Solo Surakarta style, and Pak Takim from Wojowarno Jombang in the East Javanese style. The three men in Malang then developed their wayang making methods and were among the popular craftsmen of their time.

Furthermore, the history of wayang kulit in Malang in the 1980s is not told in this discussion because since the 1980s many craftsmen in the Malang area have died and there has not been any regeneration because of work as puppet craftsmen are no longer promising and have begun. lost to craftsmen from the Surakarta area. Most of the puppeteers in Malang during the 1980s started buying wayang from other areas, such as buying wayang from Surakarta and Yogyakarta.

The Process of Making Wayang Orang Malang: A Case Study of The Process of Making Wayang Ki Dalang Raspan From Klayatan, Malang City

The process of making wayang begins with the selection of cowhide from Sapi Jawi or Kijang leather. The reason for choosing this type of leather is because the texture of cowhide is more resilient than other types of a cow. After the skin is cleaned, it is applied after drying, then it is stored in a dry place such as in the kitchen by the people of Malang. This process is commonly called ditarang with a minimum storage time of 1 year.

When to use doll skin. The skin is cleaned by scraping it, if the skin is thick it will be diluted properly. Then the skin is then drawn with a puppet pattern and then engraved. This shadow puppet pattern can be taken from an existing puppet, or drawn directly according to the imagination of the puppet maker. Wayang that has been

inlaid before *sungging* is called *wayang putihan*. *Disungging* by using water or oil-based base paint. After that, it is clamped using a *gapit* made of horns or of wood which is joined by a braid.

Variety of Wayang Kulit in Malang

Wayang Ndusun

This puppet uses a beach pattern or *gresikan*. The distinctive feature of *wayang ndusun* is that there are differences in the interpretations of each craftsman on the *wayang* he makes. Following puppet science. For example, in the *wayang bima* by Pak Darlin, the thighs are covered with cloth motifs because they are considered not obscene, while in the *wayang bima* by Mr. Wibisono the thighs are not covered with a cloth so that they give the impression as they are.

Wayang Mangkunegaran

This shadow puppet was initiated by Malang Regent IV Surya Hadikusumo with the help of Malang cultural observers at that time. During the period of the 4th Malang Regent, Adipati VII Mangkunegara opened the widest possible access to see, observe, and research to artists, researchers, and cultural observers from all regions in Java, one of which was Malang City.

It is estimated that there are efforts to determine the cultural standardization in Malang City, for the efforts generated from the standardization process are then called the *Wayang Malangan Mangkunegaran* sect. One example of the *wayang golek* genre is the work of the Ki Reni family from Palawijen and the collection of Pak Djani from Karanglo.

Wayang Pegon/Wayang Prayung

The term *Wayang Pegon / Wayang Prayung* was popularized by puppeteers in Malang in the 1970s. It was during these years that the puppeteers in Malang began to get to know the puppet genre from Central Java which at that time was performed by well-known puppeteers such as Ki Narto Sabdo, Marto Sarip, and others.

Wayang kulit is an adaptation of various styles according to the taste of the shadow puppet maker or the consumer. The characteristics of the *pegon wayang* are the emergence of regional characteristics, the tastes of the maker or the buyer, and the effort to distinguish the works they make from other people's puppets. The knowledge of the *pegon* puppet makers is also very influential on the *wayang* they make. For example in the *Bima* puppet by Pak Wibisono from Pesanggrahan, the stone on the face of the puppet was made black like the Surakarta pattern because Mr. Wibisono had blackened *Bima's* face because he thought it was black on *Bima's* face. The face will give an impression of dignity, only different from the *Bima* puppet by Pak Dollah. from Jeruk Tasikmadu Malang City on the face of the puppet is made red or pink like the Mojokerto style.

In this *pegon* puppet, general terms used in the making of puppets are becoming known, for example, *sprinkled*, *sunggingan*, *gedahan*, *wengkon / bleger*, etc.

Some of the *Pegon / Wayang Prayung* puppet makers are educated puppeteers who have received an education.

Wayang from Other Regions

Wayang from other parts of Malang is a sub-regional style of East Java and Central Java.

The function of Wayang Kulit in Malang

Identity Politics and Social Status

Some people in Malang use wayang as their identity and social status. According to Kemala Chandakirana [12] in his article Geertz and Tribal Issues, states that:

“Identity politics is usually used by leaders as political rhetoric because we refer to it as “ natives ”who want power and they are for“ newcomers ”who have to give up power. So, in short, identity politics is only used as a tool to manipulate political mobilization tools to meet their economic and political needs ”.

In line with the above opinion, Wayang Kulit in Malang is often used as identity politics for people in Malang. For example, to build an image as a rich person, people in Malang are accustomed to collecting quality wayang. The goal is that the puppets are then lent and used by the puppeteers in their performances. Wayang kulit owners feel that their name will be lifted if the wayang they use gets recognition from the public. Not infrequently in the 1980s, some rich people in Malang deliberately bought wayang kulit from Surakarta as a political identity that they shared with the rulers at that time.

Commercial

In the 1970s, wayang was a profitable commodity. The most striking impact of this is the emergence of new jobs in the community, namely being called pimps. Pimp is a provider of quality shadow puppets. Pimp's achievements include popularizing wayang in Malang and bringing in wayang from other regions. However, it is not uncommon for Pimp to also sell wayang which he trades to collectors both at home and abroad.

Since the 1980s, the Wayang Kulit Malang community has put forward the aspect of entertainment or aesthetic offerings as their appeal. Wayang kulit in Malang is following the motto of East Java, namely "Jer Basuki Mawa Bea" which is more financially oriented to provide welfare for the mastermind artists and their supporting artists. Wayang kulit in Malang as a commercial aspect relates to primary and secondary needs which are accommodated by certain parties.

Support Puppet Show

Wayang kulit is used to fulfill performance needs following the principles of the show. In the wayang kulit in Malang, a wayang is a vital tool as a means of convincing the audience and directing the audience to the atmosphere to be built.

The mismatch between the visualization of wayang characters and the narrative of the puppeteers in wayang parades in Malang often occurs. For example in the Ramayana series, the character Kresna is used for the character Rama, the figure of Setyaki for the character Anggada. As a result, several puppeteers in Malang later doubled as wayang craftsmen and added to their puppet collections according to their imaginative tastes. The size of the puppets that are made does not have a definite size, but a size that is considered based on the aesthetic sense that will be generated, for example, the feeling of being manly, alus, cheap, cruel, and so on.

As a support for the shadow puppet show and the puppeteer as a craftsman, sometimes a dalang's mischievous form appears to color his work, for example when the puppeteer was a dwarf, some of his puppets worked on important figures such as Gathutkaca, Rahwana, et al. . It is as if they are made small but with authority so that the perception is awakened that small people still look handsome.

Ritual

The shadow puppet show from the time of the ancestors functions as a ruwatan. This is seen in the function of the puppet show itself as a bodyguard in a religious ceremony in the past. Wayang as ruwatan is associated with ceremonies in the human life cycle, namely: marriage, birth, and so on.

Wayang kulit is a ritual medium often uses sacred puppets, for example, the arjuna leather puppet made from cow skin belonging to Mbah Tomo Bareng Malang. There is also a puppet show from the sacred Babatan village, it is said that the puppet was made by Sungging Purbengkoro. There is also the puppet show Bathara Kala Ki Suwito from Singosari Randaagung which is used in the pangruwatan musical instrument.

In the case of wayang making, there are also sacred shadow puppets in Malang, namely Bathara Kala, Semar, and Bathara Guru, which in the manufacturing process must have slametan and fasting facilities.

Wayang Kulit Craftsmen in Malang

In the table below, there are several lists of shadow puppet craftsmen who have been recorded during the search process since 1998. Some of the craftsmen have passed away and for craftsmen who are still alive as of this writing, researchers put a tick mark on the craftsman's name as a reminder that the puppet craftsman in Malang is not extinct.

Table 1. Wayang Kulit Craftsmen in Malang

Name of Craftsmen	Year	Domicile
Sastro	1887 M	Tengger
Sastro Amijoyo ¹ , Dacin Asmorejo ² , Sumogambar ³ , Nita ⁴ , Reni ⁵	1924 M	Simpar-Poncokusumo ¹ , Jatikerto-Kepanjen ² , Karanglo ³ , Palawijen ^{4,5}

Darlin ¹ , Darso ² , Kangsen ³ , Yik Markunah ⁴ , Bromo Ano ⁵	1950 M	Jabung ^{1,2,3} , Banjarsari-Tumpang ⁴ , Simpar-Poncokusumo ⁵
Pinto ¹ , Suryo ² , Djani ³ , Wibisono ⁴ , Takim ⁵	1960 M	Ngebal-Ngantang ¹ , Wajak ² , Karanglo ³ , Pesanggrahan-Batu ⁴ , Sukun ⁵
Sapari ¹ , Dasuki ² , Isman ³ , Tulin ⁴ , Cipto ⁵ , Slamet ⁶ , Abdollah ⁷ , Raspan⁸ , Andre ⁹ , Usman ¹⁰	1970 M	Dermo-Dau ¹ , Pohbener-Wagir ² , Jatikerto ³ , Briyut ⁴ , Jatiguwi ⁵ , Lowokwaru ⁶ , Jeruk ⁷ , Klayatan ⁸ , Punten-Batu ⁹ , Dinoyo ¹⁰
Suwito¹ , Darto ² , Suud ³ , Matropi ⁴ , Slamet ⁵ , Isno ⁶ , Kondo Suharto⁷	1980 M	Randuagung ¹ , Lawang ² , Bunder ³ , Madyopuro ⁴ , Cempokomulyo ⁵ , Wajak ⁶ , Jabung ⁷
Suyitno ¹ , Supangi ² , Tirto³ , Mulyono⁴	1990 M	Wagir ¹ , Bugis-Pakis ² , Mulyoagung ³ , Dinoyo ⁴

Reflections on the Development of Wayang Kulit in Malang

The development of Wayang Kulit in Malang City seems to subvert the structure and form of the Javanese tradition. Wayang in Malang seems to continue to develop into new forms and be framed in new ways as well. Wayang in Malang is constantly being updated and reaching new audiences, generating new communities in the process.

Symbolically, claims of authenticity and uniqueness are always associated with shadow puppet shows, especially by those seeking protection from heirloom institutions, financial income from the tourism industry, or legitimacy, while responding to a dwindling audience. However, what we do know is that wayang golek is never static but needs to be continually adapted to the audience, with the context of the performance which is always changing [13].

Wayang in Malang is a show that is "always free, but still in touch, maybe even haunted by relics from the past to the present" [14]. Wayang in Malang does not appear to be folded into the realm of certain traditions, so it must be isolated from the richness of the wayang genre that exists in Indonesia.

Wayang in Malang, like other traditions, is "a consensus between the living and the dead" [15]. Wayang in Malang from the beginning of its development seemed to "tend to abolish ownership of forms, or in other cases to shake up the old jurisprudence" [16]. Wayang in Malang seems far removed from the impression of the traditionalists who still carry the national wayang associations Pepadi and Senawangi which attempt to carve regional puppet styles into the complexity of the Indonesian national wayang, as a defensive stance to sustain Indonesia's territorial cultural integrity from invading other cultures.

Wayang in Malang is always being updated and changed in ways that are sometimes subtle, sometimes dramatic. Innovation is not an opposition to tradition; change is needed to preserve tradition as important and meaningful as the sociologist Edward Shils (1981) emphasized a few years ago. In short, Wayang in Malang is an invaluable treasure trove of individual ideas that have colored the development of the traditional art of Pedalangan in Malang.

CONCLUSION

Observing and examining various facts that have been revealed in various shadow puppets in Malang, it seems that there have been attempts to make adjustments in the development of the scene, especially in the form of wayang kulit from time to time. These changes are due to something that is considered unsatisfactory, as well as other factors that cause adjustments to exist conditions.

Change is the main characteristic of fine art in general, therefore it is only natural that wayang kulit has changed various aspects, both changes in form, function, and method of processing. Therefore, the craftsmen need to make efforts so that the shadow puppets can negotiate their identity in various fields of art that exist in this era. Wayang kulit must uphold the spirit of flexibility and efforts need to be made to regenerate wayang craftsmen sustainably, and it is necessary to build a mutually beneficial symbiosis in the communities where the craftsmen live.

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